

**“SINGLE WINDOW” IS THE LOCOMOTIVE OF THE PROCESS OF
MANAGING THE PROCEDURES OF INTERNATIONAL CARGO
TRANSPORTATION**

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the problem of preparation and presentation of a significant amount of information for export, import and transit traffic. The “single window” procedure is indicated. Representing the practical application of the concept of taming information flows. The analysis of the main models of approaches to the creation of a “single window” is carried out. The GHS system. Benefits for the state from the introduction of a “single window”. Benefits for trade.*

Key words: *“Single window”. Models of the approach to the chosen concept. The GHS system. Benefits for the state and trade.*

**«ЕДИНОЕ ОКНО» — ЛОКОМОТИВ ПРОЦЕССА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ
ПРОЦЕДУРАМИ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ГРУЗОПЕРЕВОЗОК**

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Аннотация: *Статья посвящена проблеме сбора, систематизации и представления значительного объема информации в сфере экспортных, импортных и транзитных перевозок. Указана процедура «единого окна», представляющая собой практическое применение концепции упрощения информационных потоков. Проведен анализ основных моделей реализации принципа «единого окна». Система GHS. Выгоды для государства от внедрения «единого окна». Выгоды для торговли.*

Ключевые слова: *«Единое окно», модели реализации концепции, система GHS, преимущества для государства и торговли.*

In many countries, companies involved in international trade, such as exporters and importers, shippers, forwarding agencies, customs brokers, transport operators, transporters and other parties directly involved in the handling of goods, constantly have to prepare and submit to State authorities a significant amount of information and

documents in order to comply with regulatory requirements related to import, export and transit. This information and documentation often has to be sent through a number of different institutions using their own specific (manual or automated) systems and paper document samples. Such extensive requirements, together with the requirements associated with their compliance, can pose a serious burden for government authorities and the business community and can also act as a serious barrier to the development of international trade [1].

Thus, the "single window" implies the practical application of the concept of trade facilitation in order to reduce non-tariff barriers to trade and can bring immediate benefits to all members of the trading community.

From a practical point of view, the "single window" is designed to speed up and simplify information flows between traders and government agencies and bring tangible benefits to all parties involved in cross-border trade. Centralized management of a "single window" provides the relevant state bodies and institutions with the opportunity to access information or actually receive information that is relevant to solving their tasks. In addition, the participating bodies and institutions should coordinate their control measures. In some cases, a "single window" may provide conditions for the payment of relevant duties, taxes and fees [2].

The introduction of a "single window" can bring huge benefits to both governments and the trading community. For the Government, it may entail improved risk management, increased security and increased revenue while ensuring stricter compliance by traders with the established requirements. The trading community benefits from a transparent and predictable interpretation and application of rules, as well as from a more efficient use of human and financial resources, which will allow for tangible productivity and competitiveness growth.

Since this mechanism pays special attention to the issues of preliminary analysis of information and risks, its value for government agencies and traders in the context of new security requirements increases [3].

Although many business transactions and trade practices are common to all countries, it also has its own specific requirements and conditions

a single word should imply close cooperation between all participating government agencies and institutions and the trade community

A single window does not necessarily require the introduction and application of the most advanced information and communication technology (ICT), although if Governments find and adopt appropriate ICT technologies for use within a single window, this in many cases can enhance the effectiveness of trade facilitation

Fig. 1. Basic models of approaches to the creation of a "single window"

The three main models for the Single Window mechanism are:

1. A single body that receives information in paper or electronic form, distributes this information to all relevant state bodies and coordinates control measures to prevent unnecessary obstacles in the logistics chain.

Fig. 2. Model No. 1 "single body"

2. A unified automated system for the collection and dissemination of information (public or private), within which the processes of electronic collection, use and dissemination (and storage) of data related to cross-border trade are integrated. There are various possibilities:

- integrated system: data is processed within the system;

- interface system (decentralized): data is sent to the appropriate institution for processing;
- combination of integrated and interface systems.

Fig. 3. Model No. 2 "unified automated system". With the possibility of an integrated system

Fig. 4. Model No. 2 "unified automated system" with the possibility of an interface system

3. An automated information and operating system, with the help of which a trader can submit electronic trading declarations to various authorities for processing and confirmation by a single entry method.

Fig. 5. Model No. 3 "Automated information and operating system"

One of the prototypes of a "single window" in the field of international transportation can serve as a cargo community system (GHS), which is an information technology platform related to cargo transportation (import/export/transit) of any kind of cargo

passing through a port, airport or a multimodal transport complex of local or of national importance [4]. The GHS is open to all parties involved in cargo transportation and their logistics, including customs authorities. It manages a database in which information is collected, processed, stored and exchanged, and is designed to optimize cargo transportation, improve the reliability and security of trade, monitor the movement of goods and their search, as well as to facilitate customs and administrative procedures. These systems can be considered as a portal for a one-time presentation of data or an element of a "single environment" [5].

In different countries, depending on the legal, political or organizational conditions, various institutions may be selected to lead the process of creating and operating a single window mechanism. In some cases, taking into account their key role, the information and documentation they receive and the strategic position at border crossing points, it is better to choose Customs or port authorities as an institution designed to lead the development and implementation of single Window mechanisms. They can also serve as a kind of "access" channels for the purposes of receiving and coordinating the flow of information related to the implementation of all cross-border regulatory requirements [6].

With the help of a single window, it is possible to significantly simplify and facilitate, in the interests of trading enterprises and authorities, the process of presenting and sharing the necessary information in order to meet regulatory requirements related to trade. The use of such a system makes it possible to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of official control measures and reduce costs for government agencies and traders due to better resource utilization.

The Single Window mechanism makes it possible to improve the alignment of existing state systems and processes while encouraging more open and simple methods of functioning of state bodies and their work with enterprises. For example, since traders will submit all the necessary information and documents through a single access channel, it is possible to create more efficient systems for accelerated and more accurate testing and dissemination of this information among all government agencies [7]. It will also lead to enhanced coordination and cooperation between government agencies involved in trade-related activities.

Fig. 6. Benefits for the state from the introduction of the "single window" system

Thanks to the "single window" mechanism, which ensures the systematic collection of all data, it is also possible to improve the process of managing risks for control and enforcement purposes, which will increase the safety and efficiency of trade procedures. In addition, the introduction of a corresponding payment system within the framework of a "single window" ensures fast and clear payments to state bodies and institutions of the duties and other fees they receive. A "single window", which presupposes the presentation of up-to-date information on tariff rates and other regulatory and procedural requirements, will reduce unintentional errors and increase the degree of compliance by traders with the established conditions [8]. In addition, the collection and coordination of the necessary information and trade documentation through a "single window" will entail savings in human and financial resources, allowing governments to reorient resources previously used to solve administrative tasks to perform more relevant and important functions.

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Fig.7. Benefits for trade from the introduction of the "single window" system

The main advantage for the trading community is that the "single window" provides the trader with a single channel for the one-time presentation of all necessary information and documentation to all state institutions related to export, import or transit operations.

Since the "single window" allows government agencies to process the submitted information and documents faster and more accurately, as well as to collect fees, traders should benefit from speeding up customs clearance and then obtaining permission to ship their goods, thereby reducing delivery times. In addition, increased transparency and predictability may further limit opportunities for corruption in both the public and private sectors.

If the "single window" functions as a coordinating mechanism for accessing up-to-date information on current trade rules, regulations and requirements related to their compliance, it will reduce the administrative costs associated with the implementation of trade operations and ensure stricter compliance with the requirements by trading enterprises.

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